

Aesthetic experience in the light of affective affordances¹

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Abstract

Among the most pressing questions in aesthetics are those concerning the role of emotions in aesthetic experiences. In this article I try to provide an answer to this question by exploiting the explanatory potential of affective affordances. After analyzing emotionally charged aesthetic experiences in terms of arousal and expressive features, I account for the relationship between these two types of experiential qualities through affective affordances. Then, I suggest that, sensitive as they are to norms, affective affordances allow us to do justice to the evaluative nature of most aesthetic experiences.

1. Introduction

Aesthetic experiences are difficult to define. They typically involve some form of pleasure yet are not identical with pleasurable experiences; they typically involve artworks, but they are not limited to the experience of artworks; they typically involve some form of evaluation, but not all aesthetic attributions are evaluative in the same sense; they typically involve emotions, but not necessarily everyday emotions. Rather than discouraging philosophers and psychologists from exploring them, however, the elusive nature of aesthetic experiences remains a highly debated issue.

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Among the questions one is expected to address when trying to define aesthetic experiences, there are those concerning the role played by emotions and, more broadly, by affective states when we aesthetically appreciate artefacts or natural objects. If we glance at the history of philosophical aesthetics, the concern for emotions has been a signature for the Romantic period, when artists and philosophers focused on the possible ways in which aesthetic experience could involve feelings. However, discussions about whether emotions are or not necessary conditions for aesthetic appreciation are far from settled. Rather than taking side about whether all aesthetic experiences involve emotions, this article focuses on those aesthetic experiences in which emotions seem to be involved. This does not exclude that there may exist aesthetic experiences that do not involve emotions at all. Moreover, in the same, pluralistic vein, this analysis will target aesthetic experiences in which we are in *perceptual* contact with the object (or objects) of our appreciation, but this is not in contrast with the claim that not all aesthetic experiences necessarily involve perception (e.g. Goffin 2018; Schellekens 2024).

I will first focus on two fundamental ways in which affective states partake in aesthetic experiences, namely as emotions aroused in recipients by the experienced object, and as expressive profiles of those same objects. On the one hand, there is widespread agreement that aesthetic experiences involve some kind of affective reaction, ranging from yearning in front of a tragedy, to feeling elation by listening to a musical work.³ On the other hand, many consider the emotional – or, more broadly, mental – states expressed by artists through the artworks’ material as fundamental for aesthetic appreciation.⁴ In line with the analytic literature about aesthetic properties, I will suggest that we can redescribe the emotions instantiated in those experiences in terms of *arousal properties* (§2) and *expressive properties* (§3) and argue that none of these kinds of properties⁵, taken *per se*, provides us with a satisfactory explanation of the role of emotions in aesthetic experience. Rather, I will claim that the notion of *affective affordance* functions as a powerful explanatory tool, for it manages to combine meaningfully the two kinds of affective features while at the same time accommodating the evaluative nature of aesthetic experiences (§4 and §5).

³ See Tolstoy (1897); Langer (1953); Matravers (1994); Ridley (1995); Robinson (2005); Goffin (2018) for accounts of aesthetic experiences as requiring the recipients’ affective responses.

⁴ See Collingwood (1938) and Croce (1902) for historically influential accounts of emotional expressions as being the core of aesthetic appreciation. As we will see especially in §3, expressiveness is an important aesthetic feature even for those who do not take it as a necessary ingredient of aesthetic experiences.

⁵ I will not be using the notion of “property” in any substantive nor metaphysically significant way, the term being interchangeable with “feature”, “quality”, and “character”.

Given the relevance of emotions and perceptions to many aesthetic experiences, it is surprising that there are still relatively few contributions to the aesthetic debate that refer to the notion of *affordance* to try to clarify the nature of aesthetic experiences. Shifting the perspective, ongoing discussions about affordances – and ecological psychology more broadly – tend to overlook aesthetics.⁶ Whatever the theoretical, historical, or ideological reasons for this mutual neglect, my attempt will be to link these domains of inquiry, following the intuition that they might benefit from one another. Far from suggesting that this is an entirely new strategy, I will rely on existing contributions coming from the 4E cognition literature – especially exploiting the notion of *scaffolding* – ecological psychology – leveraging the notion of *affordance* –, and psychological aesthetics that show awareness of potential exchanges between partly overlapping discussions. The narrow scope of this contribution is to outline a proposal about how affective affordances can be crucial in aesthetic experiences; the broader output is, I hope, double: a promising avenue for further research about affectivity in aesthetics, and an increased interest in aesthetic issues – broadly conceived – from the philosophy and psychology of ecological perception – broadly conceived.

2. Arousal properties in aesthetic experiences

Experiences of artworks often elicit emotional reactions in recipients. We feel moved by films, paintings, poems, musical passages, and performances. We empathize with fictional characters of literary works (Feagin 2008), we are affected by the emotional states conveyed by music (Robinson 2005), we are sexually aroused by erotic movies (Levinson 2006a), scared by horror (Carroll 1990), and amused by comedies (Levinson 2006b). We can be astounded by architectural works (Scruton 2013), upset by performances (Fischer-Lichte 2008), and, importantly, we do feel moved by natural items and environments (Carroll 1993; Menninghaus 2019). Although not all experiences we have of these artefacts and natural objects do necessarily count as aesthetically relevant, some of them do. Intuitively, at least some of these reactions can be seen as constitutive of, or at least as accompanying, experiences of

⁶ Relevant exceptions are Heft's (2024) recent attempt to bridge this gap from the perspective of ecological psychology; Gallagher's (2021) exploration of performances (both artistic and not) from an enactivist embodied perspective; Vara Sánchez' (2022) refinement of the notion 'aesthetic affordances' as distinct from affective affordances; Brincker's (2015) introduction of the notion of 'aesthetic affordances' and of a framework for aesthetic experience that is compatible with embodied and situated views on perception. Unlike these latter two accounts, I remain agnostic about aesthetic affordances. My aim is not to account for all aesthetic experiences in terms of affordances, but rather to show that the better-established notion of affective affordances can be put at the service of (at least) one aesthetic dilemma.

appreciation that we (along with a long philosophical tradition) are inclined to consider aesthetic.

The arousal of emotions in the recipients of aesthetic experiences can result in the characterization of what is sensed in affective terms: we find pitiful the destiny of those characters we worry for; we consider sexy those scenes so long as they arouse us; we deem sad those songs that make us feel the need to cry. Such attributions, I suggest, count as ascriptions of *arousal properties*. For example, one may say that:

To be impure is simply to have the disposition to cause the reactions [...] Dracula has certain properties which cause reactions of disgust, and (if impurity enters into the picture at all) it is this fact which causes the belief that the Count is impure. (Matravers 1998:93)

Or else:

An item *x* is humorous or funny iff *x* has the disposition to elicit, through mere cognition of it, and not for ulterior reasons, a certain kind of pleasurable reaction in appropriate [...] subjects generally, where this pleasurable reaction, amusement, is identified by its own disposition to induce [...] laughter. (Levinson, 2006b:396)

Given these examples, we can think of arousal properties of the considered items as those objects' actualized dispositions to arouse certain feelings. To this extent, their instantiation depends entirely on the reactions of the recipients.⁷ The arousal property of impurity ascribed to Count Dracula is not instantiated in the experience one has of it unless one feels disgust towards the fictional character. Similarly, the humorousness of a comedy line can be considered an arousal property as long as it actually causes someone to laugh at it.

Arousal properties are widespread in our experience in general, and in aesthetic experiences in particular. Nonetheless, few would be inclined to reduce the emotional component of aesthetic experiences to arousal properties. Two main reasons can be mentioned for this skepticism. First, a venerable tradition in aesthetic literature has it that aesthetic experiences are paradigmatically *detached* or *disinterested*, as opposed to instrumental (Schindler et al. 2017). Emotions are typically considered by psychology as serving some purposes, which may be of evolutionary nature, or simply limited to specific, contingent contexts: fear helps us identify

⁷ Arousal properties are distinct from the evaluative properties of emotional experiences as they are described, for example, by value dispositionalism (e.g. Smith 1989), in that they are actualized dispositions, i.e. they are instantiated only as long as the subject actually feels the corresponding emotion that is meant to realize that properties. The arousal property of sexiness is instantiated only as long as someone feels excited by the object to which it is ascribed. Instead, evaluative properties understood dispositionally do not require that subjects actually undergo the corresponding emotion, this leaving room for misattributions.

dangers and protect our offspring, disgust makes us avoid intoxications, anger discourages potential attackers, shyness signals the acknowledgement of socially required role-respecting behaviors (Frijda & Mesquita 1994). On the contrary, Immanuel Kant and his legacy famously defended that aesthetic appreciation consists in the (positive) evaluation of an object *for its own sake*, devoid of any further purpose. We should therefore refrain from characterizing those emotions featuring in aesthetic experiences as aiming at something (e.g. survival, reproduction, increase of wellbeing) beyond the pure enjoyment of the aesthetic object *per se*.

Admittedly, one way to refine and therefore preserve the role of arousal properties as crucial in aesthetic experiences is to turn to “non-standard” or “refined” emotions (Frijda & Sundararajan 2007). In addition to the already exemplified basic emotional responses to artworks, aesthetic experiences typically feature subtler, more nuanced or more complex affective reactions such as wonder, fascination, awe, interest, hesitancy, boredom, nostalgia, melancholia, and confusion (Martínez-Marín 2020).⁸ These emotions are more difficult to account for in purely instrumental terms, for they incorporate cognitive mediators like beliefs, desires, and imaginings. We can thus think of the corresponding ascriptions of charm, appeal, interest, boredom, melancholia, and disarray to a work as arousal properties that are actualized by such non-standard, intellectual emotions. Therefore, one may argue that arousal properties corresponding to non-standard emotions that are key in aesthetic experiences are in a position to exhaust the role of emotions in aesthetic experiences, because while accounting for the emotional reactions of recipients, refined arousal properties seem to dodge the skeptical claim against the fundamentally instrumental nature of emotions.

However, there is another reason for being critical against a reduction to arousal properties of the role of emotions in aesthetic experiences, namely that they do not – if taken alone – do justice to the idea that aesthetic experiences deal not only with some response on the recipients’ side, but also, and especially, with what the experienced objects appear to be like. As Malcolm Budd has argued, a theory that accounts for the aesthetic value of a work in terms of the experience the work elicits is committed to the “heresy of the separable experiences” (Budd 1985: 125), as it qualifies the work in a way that is independent from its own features. Purely arousalistic theories commit the heresy of the separable experiences so long as they characterize aesthetic experiences as something that, in principle, could be the result of ingesting a “feeling drug”, that is “a drug which arouses a feeling of a kind which is amongst

⁸ The Jamesian distinction between *coarse* and *non-coarse* emotions has been further elaborated on by Frijda and Sundararajan (2002), who name the latter *emotions with refinement*.

those characteristically aroused by [the artwork] on the basis of which it is judged to be expressive” (Matravers 1998: 170). The evaluation resulting from the feelings aroused by the drug would be only accidentally related to the nature of the work it is about. What is rather expected from a theory of aesthetic properties is that it is capable of characterizing those properties as *justifying* the experience they feature in.

Notably, this same worry can be addressed to arousalistic theories that focus on refined emotions. Take for example the case of wonder. According to Fingerhut & Prinz (2018), wonder is the emotional state that works like a litmus test for the aesthetic value of artworks. As such, wonder is not considered as a simple emotional reaction, but rather as a more complex state constituted by three “subemotional” components, namely non-emotional processes that contribute to the realization of the emotion as a whole. In this view, the subemotional components of wonder are taken to be cognitive perplexity, perceptual engagement, and a sense of reverence, which are jointly responsible for wonder disposing recipients to interact with works in certain ways (Fingerhut & Prinz 2018:116). In a similar vein, interest, considered as a refined or epistemic emotion, is seen as playing a major role in our aesthetic ascriptions. Consisting in an arousal response to novelty and complexity, interest is usually depicted as more complex than standard emotions and, as an impulse to exploration, it seems to provide a valuable contribution to aesthetic evaluations (Silvia 2005).

Complex and refined as they are, however, both wonder and interest treated as affective reactions fall prey to the heresy of the separable experiences. The fact that a work is experienced and then judged as wondrous or as interesting is, on these just sketched accounts, entirely dependent on the recipients’ responses that are, at best, causally generated by that work. These views do not provide us with ways to assess the values of the experienced artworks (or natural items) as what the experiences are about, rather than as the stimuli responsible for an effect. In the case of wonder, the subemotional component of cognitive perplexity is described as the phenomenal output of the failure in categorizing a stimulus; the perceptual engagement is exhausted by the feeling of “captivation” of the senses generated by the stimulus; and the sense of reverence is defined in terms of the attitude one is prompted to adopt when contemplating masterpieces: “we look up to them” (Fingerhut & Prinz 2018:116). Although they are meant to refine the nature of the emotion, distinguishing it from a gut reaction, these components are fully described in terms of causal responses, rather than as intentional, justifiable states about the work’s features. Interestingness, in turn, is ascribed to artworks based on the ability recipients have to deal with their complexity (Silvia 2006). And

complexity can, at first sight, be seen as the property that grounds ascriptions of interestingness. Yet, if interest is construed as an emotional reaction consisting of “emotional action tendency to spend attention and effort” (Tan 2000: 120), then the resulting ascription of the corresponding arousal property of interestingness can be entirely reduced to the recipient’s response, with no references at all to the properties of the experienced work – thereby, again, incurring in the heresy. Thus, I suggest, although it is reasonable to conceive of aesthetic experiences as involving affective arousal, there are good reasons not to reduce the affective component of aesthetic experiences to the ascription of arousal properties.

3. Expressive properties in aesthetic experiences

Not only do we react emotionally to artworks and landscapes when we deem them aesthetically relevant, but we also happen to experience them as expressive of affective states. Certain pieces of music can sound expressive of despair, romantic landscapes often look melancholy and display languid atmospheres, some abstract paintings are joyful, others express agitation. *Despair, melancholy, joy, and agitation* seem thus to characterize human emotional manifestations as well as objects’ appearances. These features have been named *expressive properties* and are commonly understood as those properties one is in contact with when experiencing an object as expressive of some psychological state (Wollheim 1994).

Although detecting expressive properties likely amounts to perceiving them (Benenti 2020), the experiences of expressive properties can be distinguished from other, more standard perceptual experiences. First of all, the way expressive properties appear in our experiences is usually seen as more subject-dependent than more standard perceptual features such as shapes, colors, or sounds. Imagine a situation of disagreement about the alleged peacefulness of a shade of color: probably the contenders will not come to an agreement on a feature that they will keep *perceiving* differently. Second, expressive features can be intentionally neglected, way more than other perceivable qualities. Consider, for example, the case of a novice musician who is so concentrated on the correctness of her execution as not to pay attention to the expressive qualities of her performance. Located on a continuum going from more stable, less subject-dependent, to less stable and more subject-dependent features, expressive qualities earn their place among the so-called tertiary qualities, that is, those that most elude measurement and emerge, gestalt-like, from underlying primary and secondary qualities (e.g. Versteegen & Fossaluzza 2018).

While most philosophers agree on these phenomenological remarks about how expressive experiences look like, the mechanisms and processes that are responsible for such experiences have been accounted for in many different, often contrasting ways. Arousalist theories argue that expressive qualities are ascribed to objects as a result of the feeling they elicit in us. In fact, they *are* arousal properties (Matravers 1998; Ridley 1995; Robinson 2005). However, this view is questionable and has been criticized on the grounds that we do not always feel moved by what we find expressive (Wollheim 1994). In other words, we can recognize expressive qualities remaining affectively neutral. This does not rule out the possibility that expressive properties move us, and that sometimes being moved helps us detect what is expressive in a work (Ridley 1995). Nonetheless, arousal responses are not a necessary condition for the detection of expressive features, this making radical arousalistic proposals hard to defend. Alternative accounts typically acknowledge that perceivable expressive profiles ground expressive experience. But while defenders of projectivist views insist that that perception is not enough to seize expressive properties, and that it must be complemented by imaginings or beliefs (Levinson 1990, 1996; Walton 1999; Noordhof 2008), perceptualist theories argue that expressive properties are perceptual saliences that inanimate objects like artworks share with expressive people (Boghossian 2007; Davies 1994, 2005; Kivy 1980, 2002; Benenti and Meini 2017; Benenti 2020).

Since I have defended perceptualist approaches to expressiveness elsewhere (Benenti 2020), here I simply insist that much of the expressive qualities that figure in our aesthetic experiences are perceived as characteristics of what we observe, be it a work of art or a natural object. That is, in experiencing expressive items, we have the impression – which can possibly be explained by resorting to disparate psychological mechanisms – that expressive qualities phenomenologically belong to the objects we encounter rather than stem from our own reaction to them. In more evocative words: “the sadness is to music rather like the redness to the apple, than it is like the burp to the cider” (Bouwsma, 1950:94). As such, do expressive properties exhaust the role of emotions in aesthetic experience? In particular, given that their instantiation does not require one to feel any emotion, but just to seize perceivable saliences resembling genuine expressions of emotions, can we be happy with expressive properties accounting for the affective side of aesthetic experiences? I think few would agree, for a couple of good reasons.

First of all, there is a widespread intuition that traverses the entire history of modern aesthetics according to which something like pleasure, appreciation, or the attribution of valence

characterizes aesthetic experiences (Robinson 2020). Whether one believes that pleasure is a condition of possibility for aesthetic appreciation, or rather that it follows or accompanies aesthetic judgement, aesthetic experience is usually thought of as *rewarding* (Levinson 2009). Such a reward is admittedly connected to some form of emotional arousal that the subject is or can become aware of. And, although they are often listed among aesthetic properties (De Clercq 2008:895), expressive properties afford fundamentally perceptual experiences that do not necessarily entail any hedonic nor valenced appreciative response. Therefore, expressive properties taken alone cannot account for the role of emotions in aesthetic experience.

The second, related aspect that is often mentioned as peculiar to aesthetic experience, and that prevents us from reducing emotionally dyed aesthetic experience to the experience of expressive features, is that the former demands us to focus our attention on the object or its properties (see Nanay 2014) and linger on it, while devoid of practical interests (Bullough 1957). In aesthetic experience we want to go back to the object again and again, to explore it and interact with it. This exploratory attitude is not compatible with the mere perceptual recognition of expressive features. We may well recognize the gaiety of a landscape, without seeing it as demanding our attention, or requesting us to interact with it, if only through the allocation of our attention. So, expressive properties conceived as perceivable aspects of what one experiences cannot per se grant this kind of effect on the recipients.

4. Affective affordances and scaffolding

Let me take stock. Arousal and expressive properties are often instantiated in our everyday experiences and, although they may go together, neither kind of property is required for the other to be instantiated. We can well acknowledge the solemnity of a public speech without feeling aroused, and we can feel the need to cry watching the news without considering them expressive of sadness. Likewise, when we listen to a piece of music, observe a painting, or attend to a ballet, the presence of arousal properties results from our emotional reactions to the work, while expressive properties can be detected in the appearances of the of the work, independently from our emotional reactions.

However, we cannot limit the role of emotions in aesthetic experiences neither to the subject's affective responses to some possibly replaceable stimuli (for the theory would fall prey to the heresy of the separable experiences), nor to the perceptual recognition of expressive profiles as merely perceptual features. Rather, we need to do justice to the interconnection between these two aspects and, most importantly, to the way in which such an interconnection result in an

invitation to sustain the experience, to make it last, and to repeat it, with the aim of aesthetically evaluating what we are experiencing. In other words, I shall show how the affective interplay between arousal and expressive features is linked to the rewarding and to the evaluative sides of aesthetic experiences. This can be fruitfully done, I submit, by mobilizing the notion of *affective affordances*.

Affective affordances have appeared relatively recently on the philosophical and psychological scene (Griffiths and Scarantino 2009; Hufendiek 2017; Krueger & Colombetti 2018 are among the seminal contributions on the topic). While affordances for action are standardly defined as those possibilities for interactions between organisms and environments (Gibson 1979/2015), affective affordances have been so far understood and explored as perceived possibilities for emotional interactions (Caravà & Scorolli 2020; Carvalho 2022).⁹ Patterned after affordances for action, they require “complementary affective dispositions”, namely affective abilities and preferences, interacting with material, cultural, and symbolic environmental saliences. Moreover, they are perceived as opportunities to modify the organism’s affective condition, by amplifying, enriching, prolongating it in time, or conversely suppressing, diluting, or avoiding it (Krueger & Colombetti 2018). For example, the spatial array of a hospital’s waiting room, with its neutral colors and its standardized plastic furniture, its cleanliness and its smell of sanitizing products may afford uneasiness in someone with previous negative healthcare experiences, but relief to somebody used to extremely precarious healthcare infrastructures. The features of the environment that are experienced as capable of modifying one’s emotional state can thus be conceived of as affective affordances. In short, affective affordances are:

Perceived opportunities for affective regulation that depend on complementary affective-dispositions of a subject and of an object or space and regulate human affectivity at the personal level. They regulate felt emotions and affective experiences, in particular their phenomenological aspects (Caravà & Benenti 2024:717).

Unlike expressive properties, that can in principle remain inert for a feeling subject, affective affordances are recognized as having the potential to move us.¹⁰ This potential is precisely what makes them affordances and the interaction they afford is affective rather than strictly action-

⁹ Notably, although the notion of “affective affordance” does not appear in James Gibson’s seminal works, it is compatible with his “radical hypothesis” that “the ‘values’ and ‘meanings’ of things in the environment can be directly perceived” and that “values and meanings are external to the perceiver” (Gibson 1979:127).

¹⁰ I have defended elsewhere a more refined view about affective affordances as incorporating expressive properties (Caravà & Benenti 2024). I am still convinced that expressive properties count as affective affordances as long as they are perceived by an organism as potential emotional regulators. What I am arguing here is precisely that this is true for aesthetic experiences.

related. However, unlike arousal properties, they cannot be reduced to the organism's affective reaction to some stimulus – such affective reactions being only among the conditions of possibility for affective affordances to emerge. Instead, affective affordances result from the interaction with our material environments that provide us with sufficient information for regulating our affective states without the need for further cognitive mediation (Griffiths and Scarantino 2009; Colombetti and Krueger 2015).

Such encounter and manipulation of our material environment with the aim of regulating our own affective condition have been described in terms of *affective scaffolding*, that is, of the creation of affective niches within which affective affordances can be perceived (Colombetti and Krueger 2015).¹¹ Although the construction of affective niches through scaffolding likely traces back to the infant-caregiver relationship (Krueger 2013; Portera 2020), most examples of affective scaffolding are provided by artefacts that we exploit for emotion regulation: from listening to music with the aim of relieving one's own mood, to seeking entertainment in movies, from consuming comfort food to rearrange furniture, from the relationship of entrenchment between professional musicians and their instruments, to the selection of clothing and wearable accessories (Colombetti and Krueger 2015).

It is thus unsurprising that the concept of scaffolding has been widely applied to theories of arts and aesthetic experiences of artefacts. Remarkable examples of this application are Michelle Maiese's (2016) psychological assessment of the use of expressive arts in psychotherapy and peacebuilding based on the scaffolded mind's hypothesis; Jussi Saarinen (2019) account of painting as a "solid" affective scaffolding to painters; Joel Krueger (2019) proposal about music's capacity to scaffold our emotional consciousness. According to these views, artistic artefacts function as material support for mental states, and especially for emotions, that are channeled, organized by, and even offloaded onto the material and worldly components of the works. Such an interaction between felt emotions and the tangible, perceivable, and usable features of artistic artifacts allows for an increase in the artist's or recipient's awareness of their own affective conditions. While painting, "[p]ainters come to expect and value certain affects during the creative process" (Saarinen 2019:74) by feeling "fused with" the work or "resonating" with it. By listening to music, listeners let their own

¹¹ Kim Sterelny's (2010) original treatment of *scaffolded cognition* highlights how organisms modify their surroundings, creating epistemic *niches* that scaffold their cognitive abilities and, in turn, influence their own development and survival. Since its introduction, the notion of scaffolding has been successfully exploited within discussions about how our mind should be considered as extending beyond our skulls to "external" supports that would thus become important if not inherent components of what are traditionally considered "mental" skills.

emotions be guided by the soundscape, possibly becoming more conscious of what they feel (or ought to feel) in specific, socially structured contexts (Krueger 2019). It is precisely within processes of emotional regulation scaffolded by artifacts that affective affordances emerge as perceived opportunities for emotional regulation.

5. Affective affordances in aesthetic experience

As we have seen, undergoing an aesthetic experience often requires that one is in perceptual contact with the expressive properties of the material object. For example, part of what it is to aesthetically experience a musical gesture amounts to perceiving its expressiveness: its alternation of tension and relaxation, its rhythm and its melody as manifesting some affective state. However, this “cold” perceptual detection is not enough to count as an aesthetic experience. Rather, aesthetic experiences paradigmatically require subjects to feel aroused in such a way that they ascribe arousal properties to the work, like when a musical gesture sounds disquieting, disturbing, or creating an uncanny atmosphere. Thus, artefacts that we experience aesthetically scaffold our feelings by presenting us with those affective affordances that emerge from the coupling between the subject’s feelings and the perceivable expressive profiles displayed by the work. From this perspective, an aesthetic experience of the first movement of Vivaldi’s *Spring* would amount to seizing its auditory features (the high-pitched trills and lively melodies of the solo violin, the sudden shift to minor tonality and rumbling lower strings, the return of the cheerful ritornello towards the end) *as affording* our own affective reactions.

Moreover, in aesthetic experiences, not only are these affective affordances perceived as capable of modifying one’s affective condition, as in everyday non-aesthetic experiences, but they are experienced as capable of affecting one’s overall perception of the work. For instance, in the aesthetic experience of a piece of pure music such as Vivaldi’s *Spring Allegro*, we not only perceive musical tension as expressive of some emotion that is capable of affecting our own emotional state, but we also see our own affective reaction of, say, increasing gaiety followed by surprise, hesitation, and then gradual relaxation, as capable of influencing our perceptual experience of the piece’s expressive profile in turn. Owing to their perceptual nature, affective affordances scaffold our feelings, which in turn guide our auditory experience of music, offering us one possible, affective perspective on its audible structure: felt gaiety, surprise, hesitation and relaxation will make us experience thrills, melodic passages, and the ritornello not only as expressive, but also as resonating with our own affective condition.

The possible resonance between the felt affective condition and the opportunity for emotion regulation offered by the perceivable profile of the work may function as an invitation to explore the work further, seeking for affective satisfaction. This, I suggest, offers a minimal explanation of how aesthetic experiences featuring affective affordances can be rewarding or pleasurable.¹² However, this should not lead us to conclude that aesthetic experiences ultimately amount to some kind of successful matching, that is, to affective affordances managing to regulate our feelings, for this does not do justice to the difference between simply emotionally rewarding experiences and aesthetic ones.

Now, compared to other affectively characterized experiences, aesthetic ones (similarly to moral ones) are usually described as *evaluative* in nature. And although this claim can be interpreted in various ways (King 2022), there seems to be a minimal sense in which we expect aesthetic experiences to ground aesthetic evaluations. When we go to a concert, we not only expect the musical performance to please us, but we also think that experiencing it will put us in a position to judge it as aesthetically valuable. This implies that our aesthetic experiences are, to some extent, guided by norms that should enable us to evaluate what we are experiencing. In what follows, I shall outline a strategy to do justice to evaluative nature of aesthetic experiences by appealing to the responsiveness of affective affordances to norms.

As it has been defended, not only do we learn to seize the affordances for action present in our environment depending on our practical goals, but we are also trained to focus our attention on the *appropriate* saliences of the environment, given our social goals (Costall, 1995; Rietveld & Kiverstein, 2014; Jacobs & Michaels 2007). This learning process requires the education of our intentions to act and interact in given, normatively structured situations (Brancazio & Segundo-Ortín, 2020; Segundo-Ortín 2022). As young children, we are taught to focus our attention on those information of the – material and social – environment that enable us to perform, for instance, our gender-related, age-related, wealth-related roles (Heras-Escribano 2019; Segundo-Ortín 2022; McClelland & Silwa 2022). The result of social training is the acquisition of skills for the perception of (only or especially) those affordances that are appropriate according to a normative environment. For instance, gender-related behaviors like “manspreading” could be explained in terms of the way in which men are typically taught to

¹² More about the kind of reward inherent to aesthetic experiences, which is especially connected to their capacity to fuel exploratory attitudes devoid of epistemic goals, has been said by Brincker (2015) and Vara Sánchez (2022). My proposal here is limited to the affective exploration prompted by resonance between expressive and arousal features.

perceive the limits of peripersonal space, neglecting other, potentially available, spatial affordances (Heras-Escribano 2019).

The possibility to account for a normative shaping of affordances suggests that also *affective* affordances scaffolded by our material environment are perceived depending on intentions to regulate our emotional conditions (Caravà & Scorolli 2020). Such intentions are arguably trained within a normatively structured social context, so that the affective affordances that emerge from focusing our attention on certain saliences instead of others are potentially evaluable as appropriate or inappropriate given contextual norms. We can for instance detect the potential that the sofa in our living-room has to alleviate our condition of restlessness, not only inviting us to snuggle up on it, but also scaffolding our feelings owing to its texture and dimensions. The sofa will thus be perceived as affording not only a bodily posture, but also affective regulation. Suppose, however, that we have never been allowed to snuggle up on a sofa, for in our cultural context people are not allowed to take on such kind of posture in public. We won't seize its potential for consolation, while probably perceive the inappropriateness of that use of the sofa.

The permeability of affective affordances to social norms helps to assess the normative side of aesthetic experiences involving emotions. For example, we hear certain musical pieces or musical styles as capable of offloading our sadness because we have learnt, within social contexts, that it is appropriate to expect from that kind of music that it scaffolds such feelings (Krueger 2019). Although experiencing affective affordances always amounts to the coupling between one's affective skills and the possibility of emotional interaction with the audible profile, different intentions could result in making us seize different kinds of affordances in the very same piece, like if we were to evaluate the aptness of the piece of music to becoming the sonic background for an event, or a movie soundtrack – instead of seeking emotional healing. The same piece whose melancholic melody results apt for scaffolding our sadness after a loss, may be heard as relaxing and pleasantly languid during a ceremony, but cheesy if accompanying a movie scene. Thus, when seizing the affective affordances of music, we are not only perceptually detecting its expressive qualities, but we are also deeming them more or less appropriate given our aim.

Social practices surrounding and channeling affective affordances have been partly explored. Not only agents' "episodic and autobiographical memories", "self-narrative" and "individual agent's affective history" (Caravà & Scorolli 2020:3) have been mentioned as responsible for the emergence of affective affordances, but also "background forces, norms, and expectations

impacting us without our full awareness and consent” (Krueger & Colombetti 2018:227), it is acknowledged, do “enable and help sustain recurring practices, modes of interaction and relational dynamics which, taken together, “realize” or “implement” affective interaction patterns and atmospheres” (Slaby 2016:8).

Admittedly, the ways in which practices and dynamics pertaining to emotions and thereby determining the education of our affective intentions deserve further study.¹³ However, admitting for the role of socially trained intentions that interact with the regulatory function of affective affordances is enough to outline their explanatory potential for evaluative aesthetic experiences. While the aesthetic experience of Vivaldi’s *Spring* can be partly unpacked as the experience of its audible expressive structure as scaffolding our emotional condition by inviting us to affectively react to its profile and listen to it guided by such a response, we must also consider that, in aesthetic experiences, our intentions are neither exclusively nor primarily aimed at emotion regulation (Vara-Sánchez 2022:76). Here is where the analysis should focus on those social practices that drive, channel, orient our approach to artworks, making us explore them (and more broadly artefacts or even natural items) as the objects of aesthetic appreciation.

Deferring an affordance-based examination of these practices to another occasion, I would like to conclude by insisting on the common trait they share, namely the evaluative expectation mentioned at the beginning of this section. When an artwork is experienced with the aim of aesthetic appreciation, the interaction it affords is guided by aesthetic expectations. These include expecting that a work complies with certain compositional rules, that it should better be attended in its entirety rather than fragmented, that it should be experienced in a given setting, that it is consistent with a genre or style – or rather challenges the rules of that genre or style – that it sounds suitable for accompanying social events or other artworks, and so on. These – and arguably further – scopes the work is expected to fulfill clearly depend on norms that are internal to the specific practices of realization and reception of different kinds of artworks (Kubala 2021). While they are not affective *per se*, they contribute to the emergence of affective affordances which are accordingly shaped by what we know, believe, have been taught about, and therefore expect from that work.

¹³ Perceptual learning is at the core of training processes resulting in improved capacity to select the information provided by the environment given one’s practical goal (Gibson 1963). Future research in ecological psychology should focus on how attention and intentions can be trained when it comes to improving our capacity to detect affectively relevant information. Aesthetic experiences could be well suited to provide such a training.

This amounts to saying that, for instance, the affective affordances offered by Jason Moran's jazz piano performance of *Reanimation* to an expert music critic will differ from those it offers to me. In the case of the expert, opportunities for emotional interaction with the piece will emerge from a complex network of aesthetic criteria condensed into aesthetic habits (Bertinetto 2025) that will enable the critic's evaluation of the work and its feature as more or less appropriate given those criteria. In the case of the novice listener like I am, affective affordances will result from less articulated – though still socially construed – expectations like being entertained, intrigued, surprised or rather bored, disappointed, bewildered by the piece. Both experiences featuring affective affordances will enable the listeners to aesthetically evaluate the piece of jazz based on the way its auditory profile scaffolds (or presents itself as capable of scaffolding) their affective conditions. Yet depending on their socially educated intentions, which in turn impose different constraints on the attentional focus, the listeners will likely experience and evaluate the same auditory material in different ways.

Conclusions

Affective affordances are a promising explanatory tool, especially when it comes to account for experiences, like aesthetic ones, where perception, emotions, and evaluation present themselves as inextricably intertwined. Importantly, I do not want to argue that affective affordances can explain aesthetic experiences in their entirety and complexity. Nor I believe that this proposal exhausts the role of affective affordances in aesthetic experiences. The scope of this contribution is rather limited to those aesthetic experiences that mobilize emotions, either in the forms of arousal features that result from affective elicitation, or in the form of expressive features detected in virtue of perceptual resemblances between a work's profile and human emotional expressions. For these experiences to count as aesthetic, it is submitted, not only arousal and expressive properties should be instantiated as interdependent, but they should also present themselves as evaluable. Affective affordance can fulfill these tasks, accounting for the way in which we emotionally interact with objects in aesthetic experiences. Consisting in the perceivable potential for emotional interaction, they feature in our aesthetic experiences in such a way that they arouse and express emotions at the same time. Moreover, liable as they are for normative guidance, they lend themselves to evaluation in the light of socially established aesthetic goals.

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